

THE VOLUNTEER WORK AND RECRUITMENT ATTRACTORS OF TEACHING OF NEWLY-GRADUATED UNEMPLOYED ENGLISH TEACHERS: A CASE STUDY OF ONE PESANTREN IN MUARO JAMBI

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Abstract

This study was part of a larger study aiming at understanding what motives possessed by voluntary teachers of English to teach at one pesantren (Islamic boarding school) in Jambi, Indonesia. The research design of this study was qualitative with a case study approach. The data were collected through demographic profiles and semi-structured interviews with twelve voluntary teachers as the participants of the study to obtain in-depth information regarding implicit and explicit motives to teaching. We analyzed the demographic data descriptively and analyzed the semi-interviews data by using within-case and cross-case displays and analyses. The interview data were digitally recorded, transcribed verbatim, and carefully analysed. The findings indicated that seven voluntary teachers of English implicit and explicit motives to teach English were motivated by interpersonal, community service, the continuation, and non-salary motives.

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1. Introduction

Education in Indonesia is managed by two ministries, the ministry of National Education and Culture and the Ministry of Religious Affairs (MoRA). Under the Ministry of Religious Affairs (MoRA), one of the educational elements that MoRa manages is Pesantren. According to the current data from the Ministry of Religious Affairs (MoRA), there are more than 15,472 pesantrens throughout Indonesia [MoRa, 2011]. The contemporarily typical Indonesian *pesantren* comprises of a *pondok* (a boarding school) and a *madrasah* (a day school) [Srimulyani, 2007]. Students in Pesantrens are called “santris” who are, according to Buang (2007), commonly memorize the Quran, the Prophet’s traditions, and Arabic classical texts or *Kitab Kuning* (yellow books) and spend their 24 hours a day in their pondok doing religious and daily activities. Additionally, a pesantren is commonly seen as a community with a complex, mosque, and boarding facility in that santris and ustazd (teachers) eat, sleep, learn, and generally interact throughout the day [Srimulyani, 2007; Buang, 2007]. On the other hand, Madrasah, an Islamic day school, is intended to teach children and youth both general/secular subjects and religious subjects as required by the Indonesian Education Law No. 20/2003. Unlike Santri, madrasah students are not required to spend their whole day at school, which allows them to socialize with their family and society [Srimulyani, 2007; Nilan, 2007].

Pesantrens in Indonesia are characteristically under privileged and santri lives in under privileged conditions and under strict rules [Nilan, 2007]. However, although Pesantrens and Madrasah are characteristically unfortunate, they still exist up to now and according to Buang [2007], they have been viewed as the last support of Indonesians' unpolluted Muslim education. One of the key elements that might keep Pesantrens and Madrasah alive is the presence of teachers who remain there regardless of low or no salary and unfortunate facility. As Lortie [1975] said that regardless of where they are placed, what subjects they teach, and what they receive, teachers are always supposed to help their students to develop their social, intellectual, and personal potentials to the higher level. Nevertheless, though Pesantrens and Madrasah are typically underprivileged, many people have actively participated and contributed to develop Indonesian human resources, particularly in rural, remote, and poor areas. This is an interesting fact. What drives people or teachers actively to participate in teaching at Pesantrens and Madrasah? What kinds of recruitment resources (motives or attractors) that attract people to go into teaching at Pesantrens and Madrasah? Lortie [1975] clearly said that any job or occupation should maintain recruitment resources consisting of the properties which assist an occupation in competing for manpower and talent. A number of previous studies have indicated that people wanting to be a teacher fall into three categories (1) altruistic reasons (reasons deal with seeing teaching as a socially worthwhile and important job), (2) intrinsic reasons (reasons cover aspects of the job activity itself), and (3) extrinsic reasons (cover aspects of the job which are not inherent in the work itself) [Chuene et al., 1999; Kyriacou & Coulthard, 2000; Low, Lim, Ch'ng, & Goh, 2011]. Additionally, Lortie [1975] found in his study that there were five attractors to teaching such as interpersonal theme, service theme, continuation theme, material benefit, and time compatibility theme.

Understanding hidden and explicit attractors to teaching, particularly teaching English voluntarily at Pesantrens and Madrasah is necessary as regardless of their strong contributions to the Indonesia education, Pesantrens and Madrasah still have lack of English teachers although it is known that teachers play a key role in developing the future of the country [Lortie, 1975; Richardson & Watt, 2006] and teachers' contribution to improve social and economic lives of any country is undeniable. Additionally, understanding hidden and explicit attractors to teaching English at Pesantrens and Madrasah is important as not many Pesantrens and Madrasah have access to have English teachers. More importantly, while there have been several recent studies examining attractors to teaching in public schools in developed countries, including US, UK, European countries, or Australia, it is somewhat surprising and regrettable that no research effort has been devoted to attractors to teaching at Pesantrens and Madrasah in Indonesia as the largest Muslim country in the world. This research project focused on looking at the hidden and explicit attractors to teaching of voluntary English teachers at the research site where a group of voluntary English teachers have being involving in teaching English at the research site since April 2015. These voluntary and young English teachers are very unique in terms of their dedication and contribution to teaching English to young learners at the research site. Although they teach the students without having any salary or payment, they keep doing their responsibilities to help their students to learn English. Looking at their dedication and contribution to teaching English to young learners, we were very interested in doing research to document what the hidden and explicit attractors attract them to do such a remarkable work.

2. The Purpose of the Study

Johnson and Christensen [2008] said, "The purpose statement of a qualitative study should be a statement that the intent of the study is to explore or understand some phenomenon experienced by certain individuals at a specific research site [p. 77]. The purpose of this study, within the attractors to teaching theory (Lortie, 1975), was to find out what had attracted voluntary English teachers to teaching English at the research site since April 2015. Specifically, the investigation centered on the hidden and explicit attractors to teaching to voluntary English teachers and centered on what keeps their commitment to teaching and what keeps them stay in the profession.

Recruitment of new teachers is one of the biggest issues in education as they are the key to success in student achievement. Lortie [1975] has written a study that cuts to the heart of the teaching profession. He examines the explicit and hidden messages that teachers are bombarded with from the earliest day that they enter the profession. Job or occupation, which does not succeed in recruiting new members, will fail to survive [Lortie, 1995]. Certain recruitment resources have to be possessed by any occupations. For teaching profession, the attractions of teaching describe the appealing characteristics in teaching for people who enter the profession. According to Lortie [1975], five attractors to teaching are presented in terms of the interpersonal, the service, the continuation, the material benefit, and time and compatibility resources.

The interpersonal resources describes the reasons for people to enter the teaching profession because it involves working and contacting with people, particularly young people in relation to the spread or diffusion of knowledge and skills. While, the resources of service are related to the teaching as a valuable service of special moral worth (the aura of its mission). The continuation resource describes the attachments to education and school, which make people to stay in school by becoming teachers. The material benefits resources such as money, prestige, rewards, salaries, social mobility, and employment security are the attractions to people who decide to choose the profession although teachers are not supposed to consider them as the major attractions. In terms of social mobility, teaching is clearly white-collar, middle-class work, and offers upward mobility for people who grew up in blue-collar or lower class families. The last, the time and compatibility attracts people to enter the teaching profession for the reason that teaching provides compatible work schedules and calendars.

The five attractors to teaching consisting of interpersonal, the service, the continuation, the material benefit, and time and compatibility resources were used to guide this study. we used every attractor as my guide in the interview protocol to get the data from the voluntary English teachers at the research site.

For this research a qualitative design with a case study approach was used to investigate the hidden and explicit attractors to teaching of voluntary English teachers at Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah where a group of voluntary English teachers have being involving in teaching English at the research site since April 2015. We chose the design because case study would allow me to explore bounded systems (cases) with in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of information (e.g. interview and observation). Creswell [2007] stated that qualitative research was carried out in natural setting without manipulating the data and kind of educational research which the researcher focuses on the views of

participants; ask general questions and the participants' experience; and provide rich narrative descriptions. Creswell [2007] stated that case study research involved the study of an issue explored through one or more cases within a bound system. For Creswell [2007], the bounded system can be restricted by time and place and the case can be a program, an activity, or individuals.

3. Sampling Procedure and Participants

Cresswel [2007] stated that non probability or purposive sampling was the method of choice for most qualitative research. Patton [1990 as cited in Christensen and Johnson, 2008] stated, "purposeful sampling is used to describe the process in develop inclusion criteria to be used in selecting participant of the research and site because individuals or cases are selected that provide the information needed to address the purpose of the research" [p. 243]. In this study, a purposeful sampling with a convenience case strategy was used. Creswell [2007] wrote, "convenience cases, which represent sites or individuals from which researcher can access and easily collect data" [p. 126]. In this study, we purposefully recruited all voluntary English teachers and to get access to them, networking with Pondok Pesantren Hidayatullah was used. The convenience case strategy is appropriate for collecting data in order to achieve the purpose of this study as participants represent voluntary English teachers at the research site. They may help us to collect the data related to their hidden and explicit attractors to teaching by sharing their feelings, thoughts, and perspectives.

In this study, twelve participants were willing to participate consisting of 2 male and 10 female newly-graduated unemployed English teachers. Eight female participants had taught in the research site since 2015 and the rest had joined since 2016. Their ages were between 23 and 24 years old. Throughout this paper, we used these pseudonyms as their identity such as Ms A or Ms B.

4. Data Collection

The primary data for my study were collected through a semi-structured interview, which were conducted individually with each voluntary English teacher based on their availability and at a location of the teacher's choice with all participants. Additionally, we had a focus group discussion and it depended on the participants' time and willingness. Of twelve participants, five participants were not interviewed directly due to their time and distance. But, they were still willing to share their motivation to join the program by asking me to send a list of questions. we sent the list of the questions and they sent their responses through emails. The five participants were Ms C., Ms K., Ms L, Mr. J, Mr. G.

2. Data Analysis

For the analysis of the data, we faced many challenges such as time to transcribe every individual's talks. we analyzed the demographic data descriptively while the interview data were transcribed individually. All the transcripts among participants were analyzed and compared to search similarities and differences. As is typical in a qualitative study, data collection and data analysis do not happen in a serial manner; rather data collection and data analysis influence each other.

The first step that we did was to do what Miles and Huberman [1994] called “within case analysis.” After I interviewed the first participant, I directly audio taped, transcribed verbatim, and carefully analysed and categorized all of the interview data into interpersonal attractors, social service attractors, continuation attractors, Non material benefit attractors expectations of no payment, and time and compatibility attractors as my coding processes. This process was continued to be done until the last participant. we read each transcript of each participant line-by-line independently, marked relevant chunks of statements, put relevant chunks of statements into the categories/themes that had been created. For example, Ms A (pseudonym) was the first participant that we interviewed. After we transcribed her interview data, we analyzed the data, and put her relevant chunks of statements into interpersonal attractors, social service attractors, continuation attractors, Non material benefit attractors/ expectations of no payment, and time and compatibility attractors that we had created. In terms of interpersonal attractors, Ms A said, “the Pesantren where I work is not a famous one. When the first time, I came there, I experienced new things such as highly motivated kids...”

Next, after we analyzed every participant’s transcript and put the data into the themes and sub-themes of each participant, then we did what Miles and Huberman [1994] called “cross-case analysis.” We reanalyzed and compared all transcripts across twelve participants in order to find the frequency of statements among participants for each general theme and for each specific theme (e.g. *interpersonal attractors, social service attractors*). We also did a “cross-case analysis in order to remove repetitive data (e.g. one participant stated the same statement several times.

In general, a variety of factors may influence the nature of one's motivations to volunteer as volunteerism is the willingness of people to help others without any sort of expectations of payment or any other tangible gain [Munro, 2001]. Four basic reasons for volunteering were Altruistic, Market, Cause serving and leisure [Parker, 1997] while Clary, Snyder and Stukas [1996] suggested social, value, career, understanding enhancement and protective were the six broad motivational functions for people to volunteer. In education, especially, in teaching each individual who may be recruited to teach is influenced by several attractors or factors. Lortie [1975] found in his study five attractors to teaching consisting of interpersonal, the service, the continuation, the material benefit, and time and compatibility resources.

References

- [1] Armanios F 2003 Islamic Religious Schools, Madrasas: Background *CRS Report RS21654 Congressional Research Service, the Library of Congress* Retrieved January 10 2012 from <http://www.policyalmanac.org/world/archive/madrasas.pdf>
- [2] Blanchard C M 2006 Islamic Religious Schools, Madrasas: Background *CRS Report RS21654 at the second session of the 109th Congress Congressional Research Service, the Library of Congress* Retrieved January 10 2012 from <http://www.fas.org/sgp/crs/misc/RS21654.pdf>
- [3] Bogdan R C and Biklen S K 1998 *Qualitative Research for Education: An Introduction to Theories and Methods (3rd ed.)* (Boston: Allyn and Bacon)

- [4] Bruinessen M V 1994 Pesantren and Kitab Kuning: Maintenance and Continuation of A Tradition of Religious Learning in W. Marschall(ed.) *Texts from the islands.Oral and written traditions of Indonesia and the Malay world* 121-145 (Berne: University of Berne)
- [5] Bruinessen M V 2004 Traditionalist and Islamis Pesantrens in Indonesia Paper presented at the workshop on the Madrasa in Asia, transnational linkages and alleged or real political activities (ISIM: Leiden)
- [6] Buang S 2007 Madrasah and Muslim Education: Its Interface with Urbanization In W. T. Pink and G. W. Noblit (Eds.) *International Handbook of Urban Education* 321–342 (New York: Springer)
- [7] Creswell J W 1998 *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing among Five Traditions* (Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc)
- [8] Creswell J W 2007 *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing among Five Traditions.* (Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc)
- [9] Denzin N K 1989 *Interpretive Biography* (Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications, Inc)
- [10] Lortie D 1975 *Schoolteacher: A Sociological Study* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press)
- [11] Lukens-Bull R 2001 Two Sides of the Same Coin: Modernity and Tradition in Islamic Education in Indonesia *Anthropology and Education Quarterly* **32** 3 350-372
- [12] Marshall C dan Rossman G B 1999 *Designing Qualitative Research* (3rd ed.) (Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage)
- [13] Ministry of Religious Affairs 2011 *Data Pesantren* Retrieved February 17 2012 from http://www.ditpdpontren.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=76&Itemid=57
- [14] Ministry of National Education.(2003). *Law for education No.20/2003*. Jakarta, Indonesia: Department of National Education.
- [15] Nilan, P. (2009). The Spirit of Education in Indonesian Pesantren *British Journal of Sociology of Education* **30** 2 219-232
- [16] Raihani 2001 *Curriculum Construction in the Indonesian Pesantren* Doctoral Dissertation (University of Melbourne, Australia)
- [17] Srimulyani E 2007 Muslim Women and Education in Indonesia: The Pondok Pesantren Experience. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education* **27** 1 85–99
- [18] Tan C 2011 *Islamic Education and Indoctrination: The Case in Indonesia* (New York: Routledge)

